

Lab Manual (Organic Chemistry)

Multistep Organic Synthesis

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Experiment No 1

Preparation of cyclohexanone oxime (cyclohexanone, oxime; antioxidant D; ncyclohexylidenehydroxylamine)

Principle:

Cyclohexanone oxime is an [organic compound](#) containing the functional group [oxime](#). This colorless solid is an important intermediate in the production of [nylon 6](#), a widely used [polymer](#).

Theory:

Oximes are common chemical intermediates. The oxime we are making is used commercially in synthesis of nylon-6. Nylon-6 is a major industrial chemical which is used to make car tire tread and shoe laces. Oximes have also shown to have promise as drugs which reduce the harmful impact from deliberate.

Mechanism:

Apparatus:

Beaker, measuring cylinder, conical flask, hot plate, magnetic stirrer, filter paper.

Chemical required:

- Hydroxyl amine hydrochloride,
- sodium acetate
- water and ice
- cyclohexanone

Procedure for preparing cyclohexanone oxime hydrochloride and sodium acetate:

How to prepare oxime hydrochloride and sodium acetate

1. Dissolve 2 g sodium acetate in 100 ml of water.
2. Heat the mixture until it boils.
3. Add 7.5 g oxime hydroxylamine.
4. Place the flask in the refrigerator and shake for 10 minutes.
5. Let the mixture cool.
6. Dissolve the oxime in cold water.
7. Wash the oxime with cold water.

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \frac{\text{Actual yield}}{\text{Theoretical yield}} \times 100$$

$$\% \text{age yield} = 0.8374 \times 100 / 1.44$$

$$\% \text{age yield} = 58.1\% \text{ **Result:**}$$

1.25g of cyclohexanone is converted into 58.1% oxime

Experiment 2

Preparation of Caprolactam from Oxime by Beckmann

Rearrangement:

Theory:

The Beckmann rearrangement is an organic reaction used to convert an oxime to an amide under acidic condition. The reaction begins with protonation of the alcohol group forming a better leaving group. The group Trans to the leaving group then migrates to the nitrogen resulting a carbocation and attack of H₂O molecule to the carbocationic centre and then tautomerization occurs and amide product is formed.

Here also caprolactam has been formed by Beckmann rearrangement from cyclohexane oxime.

Majorly it is used to make Nylon-6 filament, fibre and plastics.

Chemicals required:

1. Cyclohexane oxime
2. Concentrated (85%) H₂SO₄
3. 25% KOH solution
4. DCM
5. Phenolphthalein
6. 10% Ethyl acetate/Petroleum ether.

Apparatus required:

1. 500 ml beaker
2. Dropper
3. Buchner funnel
4. Filter paper 5. Separating funnel

Reaction:

Mechanism:

Procedure:

- Prepare the 85% sulfuric acid by adding 50 mL of the concentrated acid cautiously to 10 mL of water.
- Cool the diluted acid in ice-water and place 4 mL of the cold acid in a 250 mL beaker.
- Add 2 g. of the pure oxime and warm the mixture cautiously until effervescence begins, and then at once remove the heat.
- A vigorous reaction occurs and soon completed.
- Cool it in ice-salt bath and add some of crushed ice to the mixture and stir it mechanically whilst slowly adding 25% aqueous potassium hydroxide solution until the mixture is faintly alkaline to phenolphthalein to ensure that the temperature does not rise above 20 °C.
- During this operation a considerable amount of potassium sulphate crystallizes from the mixture.
- Filter the latter at the pump and wash the residual sulphate on the filter with 20 ml. of DCM. • Run the filtrate into a separating funnel and separate the DCM layer.

- Extract the aqueous layer three times with DCM, using 20 mL on each occasion.
- Dry the united DCM extracts with sodium sulphate and check TLC and concentrate the extract in vacuo.
The caprolactam, mp 68-70 °C **Characterization:**

- Check TLC with appropriate solvent.

- Record IR Spectroscopy • Record NMR Spectroscopy **Calculation:**

From calculation equation

Cyclohexanone convert itself to an amide (caprolactum) by Backmann rearrangement **Theoretical yield**

113.6g of cyclohexanone oxime form caprolactum = 113.6g/mol

1g of cyclohexanone oxime form caprolactum = 113.6/113.6

2g of cyclohexanone oxime form caprolactum = 113.6 x 2/113.6

Theoretical Yield = 2 g

Actual yield of caprolactum = 0.8374g

%age yield = $\frac{\text{Actual yield}}{\text{Theoretical yield}} \times 100$

%age yield = $\frac{0.8374}{2} \times 100$

%age yield = 41.87% **Result:**

2g of cyclohexanone oxime is converted into 41.87% caprolactum

Experiment No 3

Synthesis of Para Red

Apparatus:

Beaker, stirrer, weighing balance, Hot plate, filter paper, funnel.

Chemicals:

2.7g Naphthol

2.5M NaOH

1M Sulfuric acid

Mechanism:

P nitro aniline

Diazotization of p- nitroaniline:

- In a 250 mL flask, combine 5 mL of strong sulfuric acid with 50 mL of water.
- While adding 5.0 g of p-nitroaniline, swirl the mixture. To chill the flask to 5 to 10 °C, place it in an ice bath.
- Slowly add 2.5 g of sodium nitrite solution in 10 mL of water while rotating the mixture.
- Hold on the reaction's temperature in an ice/salt water bath below 10 °C by changing the pace at which the solution of sodium nitrite.
- Maintain the ice-water bath's temperature below 10 °C so that the diazonium salt does not break down before you're ready to use it in the subsequent steps.
- Avoid attempting to describe the salt.

Dyeing Cloth samples with para red:

- Put 100 milliliters of boiling water in a beaker with 0.5 grams of 2-naphthol in it.
- Swirl the mixture and add 2.5 M NaOH solution dropwise until about 3/4 of the 2-naphthol dissolves. (A little bit more than one milliliter of NaOH ought to work.) Avoid adding too much alkali as this might lead to the disintegration of your cloth.
- Use 15 mL of cold water to dilute 5 mL of the cold diazonium salt solution.
- Using a stirring stick, thoroughly moisten a piece of cotton fabric with the diluted solution and let it sit for a few minutes.
- Using forceps, remove the cloth, then drag it down the inside edge of the beaker to drain out some of the extra fluid. Fill 50 mL with the cloth.

Preparation of Para Red:

- Dissolve 2.7 g of 2-naphthol in 50 ml of 2.5M NaOH solution.
- Cool the solution to 10 °C by adding crushed ice.
- Carefully pour this solution into the flask containing the remainder of the diazonium salt, while swirling.
- Continue to swirl the mixture vigorously for a few minutes, then acidify it with 1 M sulfuric acid.
- Collect the red precipitate by vacuum filtration. Wash the product with water under vacuum filtration and allow it to air-dry.
- Because Para Red decomposes upon melting, you should not obtain its melting point.
- Record IR and ¹H NMR spectra of the pure product.

Calculation:

p nitroaniline
1 mole

para red

Theoretical yield

138.12g of p-nitroaniline forms para red = 293.28 g

1g of p-nitroaniline forms para red = $293.28 \text{ g} / 138.12$

2.5g of p-nitroaniline forms para red = $\frac{293.28}{138.12} \times 100$

Theoretical yield of para red = 5.30g

Actual yield of para red = 4.86g

%age yield = $\frac{\text{Actual yield}}{\text{Theoretical yield}} \times 100$

%age yield = $\frac{4.86}{5.30} \times 100$

%age yield = 90.9%

Result: 2.5g of p-nitroaniline forms 90.9% para red dye.

Experiment No 4

Synthesis of Fluorescein:

Principle:

Here a modified Friedel-Crafts acylation reaction is occurring. This reaction is a series of electrophilic aromatic substitutions, with hydroxyl leaving groups picking up protons by Lewis acid catalysis. It increases the electrophilicity of phthalic anhydride in the first step, and facilitates the elimination of the hydroxyl groups. In order to get the form of the molecule shown as the product of the reaction, the pH needs to be increased in order to open the lactone ring.

Apparatus

Conical flask, Beaker, pipette, Buchner funnel, glass.

Chemicals:

- Phthalic anhydride
- Resorcinol
- Anhydrous zinc chloride
- Concentrated hydrochloric acid
- Sodium hydroxide

Reaction:

Mechanism:

Procedure:

- Taking conc. H₂SO₄ instead of anhydrous zinc chloride and conc. hydrochloric acid.
- Take 0.2 g of phthalic anhydride, 0.3 g of resorcinol in dry conical flask.
- Add 6 drops of 4N H₂SO₄ and heat in a preheated oil bath to a temperature between 180° and 200°C for half an hour avoiding overheating.
- Cool the reaction mixture for 5 min. When the temperature is about 80° add 10 ml acetone and stir vigorously for 5- 10 min. The solution should turn yellow as the crude fluorescein dissolves. If the entire product did not dissolve, repeat the process with an additional 5 mL of acetone.
- Combine the acetone layers in a 50 mL beaker and Boil off the acetone leaving a crude orange residue. Dissolve the residue in 30 mL of diethyl ether and 1.5 ml of water.
- Stir for several min, separate the layers using separatory funnel adding 15 ml water and extract the ether layer once with 10 mL of a saturated NaCl solution.
- Pass the organic layer over anhydrous sodium sulfate and evaporate to dryness in a water bath.

Calculation:

Theoretical yield

148.1g of phthalic anhydride form fluorescein = 332.31g

1g of phthalic anhydride form fluorescein = 332.31/148.1

of phthalic anhydride form fluorescein = $\frac{332.31 \text{ g}}{148.1} \times 5$

Theoretical yield = 11.22g

Actual yield of fluorescein = 10.74g

Actual yield

$$\begin{aligned} \text{\%age yield} &= \frac{\text{Actual yield}}{\text{Theoretical yield}} \times 100 \\ \text{\%age yield} &= \frac{10.74}{11.22} \times 100 \\ \text{\%age yield} &= 95.72\% \end{aligned}$$

Result: 5g of phthalic anhydride form 95.72% fluorescein

Experiment No. 5

Synthesis of Benzoic Acid

Principle:

Benzoic acid is simplest aromatic carboxylic acid. It is used for the preparation of various important compounds. Itself it acts as catalytic and antifungal agent.

Apparatus:

Beaker, Round bottom flask, Condenser, Filter paper, Funnel, Tripod stand

Chemicals:

- Benzamide 1g, NaOH 10% Solution (15ml), Conc H₂SO₄

Reaction:

Procedure:

- Placed the mixture of conc. NH₃ (10 mL) and water (5 mL) in a conical flask & shake vigorously and add benzoyl chloride drop by drop formed the benzamide as separated.
- Take 1 gm of formed benzamide & 10 % NaOH (15 mL) in a RBF flask fitted with refluxes condensers and boil the mixture gently 30 min. ammonia is evolved then add con.
- H₂SO₄ after cooling the mixture until it becomes acidic and benzoic acid is immediately separated out.

Calculation:

Theoretical yield:

121.139g of Benzamide produce benzoic acid = 122.12g

1g of Benzamide produce benzoic acid = $122.12\text{g}/121.139$

8g of Benzamide produce benzoic acid = $\frac{122.12}{121.139} \times 8$

Theoretical yield = 8.06g

Actual yield = 5.4g

%age yield = $\frac{\text{Actual yield}}{\text{Theoretical yield}} \times 100$

%age yield = $\frac{5.4}{8.06} \times 100$

%age yield = 66.99%

Result:

8g of Benzamide form 66.99% benzoic acid.

Experiment No. 6

Determination of saponification number Principle:

On refluxing with alkali, triacylglycerols (fatty acid esters) are hydrolyzed to give glycerol and potassium salts of fatty acids (soap). Such process is known as, Saponification. The saponification equation is shown below:

The saponification value is the number of milligrams of KOH required to neutralize the fatty acids resulting from the complete hydrolysis of 1g of fat.

The saponification value gives an indication of the nature of the fatty acids constituent of fat and thus, depends on the the average molecular weight of the fatty acids constituent of fat. The greater the molecular weight (the longer the carbon chain), the smaller the number of fatty acids is liberated per gram of fat hydrolyzed and therefore, the smaller the saponification number and vice versa.

Material:

- 1- Fats and oils (olive oil, coconut oil, sesame oil, and butter)
- 2- Fat solvent (equal volumes of 95% ethanol and ether)
- 3- Alcoholic KOH (0.5 mol/liter)
- 4- Reflux condenser.
- 5- Boiling water bath.
- 6- Phenolphthalein.
- 7- Hydrochloric acid (0.5 mol/liter)
- 8- Burettes (10 ml and 25 ml)
- 8- Conical flasks (250ml)

Procedure:

- 1- Accurately weight 1g of fat in a small beaker and dissolve it in about 3ml of the fat solvent.
- 2- Quantitatively transfer the contents of the beaker to a 250 ml conical flask by rinsing the beaker three times with a further milliliters of solvent.
- 3- Add 25ml of alcoholic KOH and attach to a reflux condenser.
- 3- Set another reflux condenser as blank with everything present except the fat.
- 4- Heat both flasks on a boiling water bath for 30 min.
- 5- Leave to cool to room temperature and titrate with 0.5 mol/liter HCl and use phenolphthalein as indicator. Until the pink color disappears.
- 6- Record your readings as T ml for test and B ml for blank.

Calculation:

The difference between blank and the test reading gives the number of mm of KOH required to saponify 1g of fat

1ml of (0.5 N HCl) = 28.05mg KOH

(B-T) = S

Formula

$$\text{Saponification value} = \frac{(B-T) \times 28.05}{\text{of fat g}} \text{ wt}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{(23-20) \times 28.05}{1} \\ &= 84.15\text{g} \end{aligned}$$

Result: The saponification value is 84.15g.

Experiment 7

Estimation of amide group

There are different methods for estimation of amide groups present in organic compounds.

However one such method is present . Which can be easily performed in lab. Here in this experiment. We will find out number of amide group present in organic compound of unknown molecular weight.

Principle

Amides are estimated in laboratories scale by saponification methods. Mostly primary amides are analyzed by this method. Where an amide is heated with caustic soda to liberate ammonia. Then this free ammonia is absorbed by acid to form a salt. While the unreacted acid is determined by titration method. Thus amount of NH_3 is liberated gives the amount of (amide group) in given unknown acid.

Process:

- Weight out 1.0 gram of unknown organic compound (MW_t 121gm amide) in 250ml round bottom flask and add 20 ml of 1M NaOH.
- Reflux the flask using water condenser for 30 minute. Till all ammonia gas is evolved. Then titrate this solution against 1M HCl using Phenolphthalein as an indicator till solution becomes colorless.
- Also titrate a blank solution having 20ml of 1M NaOH against 1M HCl using same indicator.

Reaction:

Calculation:

100ml of 1M NaOH requires = 100ml of 1M HCl
1ml of 1M NaOH requires = 1 mole of NH₃
Weight of O.C (anide) = 1gm
Molecular weight of O.C (amide) = 121gm
Lets say
1M HCl = volume used = 20ml
1M HCl = blank volume used = 30ml
Actual weight of 1M HCl used = 10ml
1000ml 1M NaOH = 1 amide group
10ml 1M NaOH = 1/1000 × 10
= 1/100 = 0.01 amide group
1.0gm of O.C has = 0.01
121gm of O.C has = 0.01/121
= 1.21 amide group
1.21 ~ 1 amide group

